

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVING FOREIGN LANGUAGE MEMORIZATION

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Study in Support of Foreign Language Learning

Abstract

Learning foreign languages is a challenge. The process of learning a foreign language is long and accompanied by difficulties. The main difficulty stems from memorizing foreign words, their meanings in the native language, and their active use. Poor memory is a natural human quality that has its own explanation, as well as importance from the point of view of studying the abilities of the human brain to acquire foreign languages. The present article makes recommendations for improving memory's ability to memorize foreign language knowledge more quickly and permanently. The recommendations refer to the implementation of implicit and explicit methods of foreign language learning, as well as multistage memorization of foreign words. Implicit learning involves acquiring knowledge unconsciously through exposure, while explicit learning requires conscious effort and study. By combining these approaches, learners can enhance their retention and use of new vocabulary. Additionally, repeated exposure and practice across multiple stages can reinforce memory and ensure long-term retention of words.

Keywords: foreign language memorization, forgetting foreign language knowledge, implicit and explicit foreign language learning methodologies, building passive and active vocabulary

1. Introduction

When learning a foreign language, the primary concern is the effectiveness of its acquisition. Given its importance and the need for understanding, this issue is a serious topic for discussion. The main problem in this area is the human tendency to forget, which emphasizes the importance of memorizing a foreign language. In principle, learning a foreign language takes place in two ways, which can be applied separately or in combination with different proportions and sequences. The learning process is complex and involves implicit and explicit methods, each with advantages and disadvantages. It is incorrect to ignore either of them or give preference to one over the other.

Learning a foreign language implicitly does not require a teacher's participation, but this does not mean teachers should not use this method in their teaching process. Implicit learning happens naturally, like how we acquire our native language through immersion and context. Explicit learning, on the other hand, is structured and systematic, requiring direct instruction from a teacher. Following these methods, learners can self-study the language implicitly while also learning regularly with a teacher explicitly. This dual approach can maximize the effectiveness of language acquisition.

The studied language may fall into the same category as the learner's native language, or it may be entirely different. These factors are essential for determining which strategies learners should choose. Different approaches are required for the memorization and acquisition of foreign languages related to vocabulary and grammar. Foreign word acquisition requires memorization, while grammar acquisition requires understanding

and memorization through studying grammar rules and practical exercises. The implicit method is particularly effective for learning vocabulary, while the explicit method is more suitable for grammar. Implicit language learning mirrors the natural process of acquiring a native language orally, whereas explicit learning is like formal education, which enhances these skills through reading and writing.

Typically, people learn foreign languages explicitly by attending schools or language courses. This structured approach often brings challenges in terms of memorization and acquisition. Effective language learning involves overcoming these challenges through appropriate strategies, addressing both passive and active language knowledge. Active language vocabulary includes words and expressions that learners can actively use when speaking and writing. Passive language vocabulary includes foreign words that learners understand when listening or reading but cannot actively use.

The human tendency to forget is a significant obstacle to language acquisition, particularly for vocabulary retention. We should design learning processes to prevent the fading of foreign words. Natural human memory fades over time, causing a loss of foreign language knowledge; some words from active vocabulary transition to passive vocabulary, thereby reducing fluency. *An empirical rule suggests that human memory fades most rapidly in the hours and days following the initial learning of new foreign words. However, anything retained after a month is more likely to persist long-term.*

To address these challenges, learners should implement strategies that reinforce memorization and retention. This involves regular review sessions and practical usage of the language, ensuring that newly learned words and grammatical structures remain active in the learner's mind. By balancing implicit and explicit learning methods and continuously engaging with the language, learners can effectively manage and overcome the natural tendency to forget, thereby enhancing their overall fluency and later proficiency in the foreign language.

2. General recommendations for foreign language learning during its different levels of fluency and later proficiency.

General recommendations for acquiring a foreign language include combining implicit and explicit learning methods and adjusting the proportions based on the learner's current proficiency level, as per the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). CEFR categorizes language ability on a six-point scale, from A1 for beginners to C2 for mastery. [1]

Before starting at level A1, learners should spend a short period, say 1-2 months, engaging in brief audio or preferably video lessons for beginners, lasting 30–40 minutes each day. Numerous free videos on YouTube cater to this purpose, aiding learners in familiarizing themselves with the language. When chosen wisely videos such as cartoons with sound and subtitles can facilitate implicit learning, enabling learners to grasp the first 20–30 words effortlessly.

It is recommended to start an appropriate course with a teacher for beginners at the A1 level. Explicit teaching by instructors proves to be the most effective and efficient method for learning grammar. However, a drawback of this method is exposure to incorrect pronunciation and grammatical errors from fellow students, which are inevitable in group settings. To circumvent such issues, opting for one-on-one private lessons solely focusing on grammar is advisable.

As learners progress to level A2, explicit teaching continues in a similar manner to level A1. Typically, the vocabulary range for English levels A1 and A2 falls between 350 and 750 words, contingent on the number of lessons. Balancing vocabulary acquisition and grammar learning at a ratio of 50:50 is essential during this phase. Additionally, engaging in daily self-study through listening to audio stories and watching relevant video materials is crucial. Immersing oneself in the language facilitates vocabulary expansion, as learners comprehend foreign speech and grasp unfamiliar words in context.

To complement grammar lessons with a local teacher, students can opt for additional one-to-one sessions with instructors from online platforms like Italki.com, which offers quality services at reasonable prices. This approach minimizes the adverse impact of group learning on pronunciation. It is good to encourage students to practice their active language skills during these one-to-one sessions, incorporating unfamiliar words into their vocabulary for further study and assimilation.

Lessons for B1-B2 levels resemble those of previous levels, with continued listening practice, but also include added reading comprehension. At these levels, grammar instruction should be explicit, incorporating exercises and guidance from the teacher. After advancing to B2 and C1 levels, learners should approach grammar study academically, under the supervision of instructors. In addition to studying explicit grammar, learners should also practice implicit grammar rules through reading comprehension exercises.

In conclusion, a balanced approach combining implicit and explicit learning methods, tailored to the learner's fluency and later proficiency level, is essential for effective foreign language acquisition. Engaging with both structured lessons and immersive materials will ensure a well-rounded development of language skills.

3. Basic Stages of Foreign Word Acquisition and Knowledge Transition from Passive to Active Vocabulary

We learn foreign words by listening, reading, and writing texts and using visual dictionaries that present each word in written form with a picture. Using word cards and repeating perusal dictionary reading is common practice. Utilizing all available methods to acquire foreign words is also good, ensuring easy and permanent memorization. Consistent exposure and practice are key to retaining new vocabulary. Furthermore, engaging in conversations and using practical language reinforces memory and understanding.

3.1. Listening to Unfamiliar Words:

Listening to unfamiliar words several times without knowing their meaning in one's native language is the first step. The goal is for the listener to tune their ears to the sounds. Hearing a foreign word repeatedly helps with its memorization, causing the listener to perceive it as familiar each time they listen to it. This is the first stage of familiarization with a foreign word. This stage helps in acclimating the learner to the phonetic structure of the new language.

3.2. Using Expressions with Unfamiliar Words:

Expressions need to include unfamiliar foreign-language words. For learners, it is important to understand the meaning of unfamiliar foreign language words in context, but the difficulty level of these expressions must align with their level of knowledge; otherwise, resorting to a dictionary, which can be distracting, is not the best approach. Contextual learning helps associate new words with known concepts, making it easier to remember them.

3.3. Using Dictionaries and Digital Tools:

At a later stage, learners should use dictionaries to study unfamiliar words in depth and understand their basic and broad meanings and applications. Furthermore, some digital dictionaries have sound applications that allow users to hear the word. Some dictionaries offer sentence examples, which greatly aid in understanding the correct meaning of the word and facilitate its memorization. This marks the second stage of learning an unfamiliar word. Using sentence examples helps you understand the word's proper usage and nuances.

3.4. Repeated Memorization:

Memorization is not a single act, and to be efficient, it is necessary to repeat many times what we have learned. Plan and spread out the repetitions over a month to help the learner's passive memory absorb the information. This method leverages the spacing effect, which improves retention by increasing intervals between review sessions. Consistently revisiting the material reinforces the information, increasing its likelihood of retention in long-term memory. The best way to do this is by listening and reading comprehension of proper learning materials, including watching TV or interesting videos that attract the learner's interest and curiosity. This is a permanent task, and we can refer to it as the third stage of foreign word acquisition, which is a bridge to the fourth stage of building foreign language passive vocabulary.

3.5. Transition from Passive to Active Memory:

Once learned, a foreign word typically enters passive memory. If you use or hear the words often, they can enter active memory. We must consider as an empirical rule that passive foreign language study through listening comprehension and reading comprehension generally leads to the enhancement of passive memory only. The percentage of passive words that unconsciously move into active memory is low. To improve active vocabulary, one must engage in active usage, such as speaking or writing, which reinforces the learned words through practical application. This is the fourth stage of foreign word acquisition or developing an active foreign-language vocabulary. The best way of doing this is through active use of the foreign language, which includes communication and verbal and written translation from the native language into the foreign language.

3.6. Building Active Vocabulary:

Foreign word Active vocabulary building is the last stage of memorization. It necessitates the active use of foreign words. This could be accomplished through dialog, oral, or written translations from a native language into a foreign language. The active foreign language vocabulary is based on passive vocabulary. Only after repeated use of passive words and their active use in speaking and writing can we expect to enhance active vocabulary. Practical usage solidifies the transition of words from passive to active memory. The level of fluency and proficiency in a foreign language measures the permanent process of building an active vocabulary.

Active vocabulary building is the final stage of memorization for acquiring foreign words. It requires actively using these words in various contexts. Dialogue, oral practice, or written translations from one's native language into the foreign language can achieve this active utilization of foreign words. A language builds its active vocabulary on its passive vocabulary. Mastery of words, initially encountered passively, only comes after repeated use in speaking and writing. Practical application further solidifies the transition of words from passive to active memory, reinforcing language acquisition. "The development of active vocabulary is an ongoing process in foreign language acquisition, measured by one's fluency and proficiency in the language.

3.7. Maintaining Vocabulary:

If we don't regularly use some words in our active vocabulary, they may revert to their passive form. Regular practice and usage are crucial to maintaining an active vocabulary. Reviewing and using words in different contexts helps keep them active and prevents them from fading back into passive memory. Regular active and passive language use can help maintain foreign language vocabulary.

Interim Conclusion:

In the journey of foreign word acquisition, transitioning from passive to active vocabulary involves several crucial stages. Initially, exposure through listening, reading, and visual aids helps familiarize learners with new words. As a result, contextual understanding, and the use of unfamiliar words in expressions facilitate deeper comprehension. The use of dictionaries and digital tools expands knowledge, while repeated memorization techniques strengthen retention. As learners progress, active usage through speaking and writing bridges the gap between passive and active memory, culminating in the building of an active vocabulary. This process is dynamic and ongoing, requiring consistent practice and engagement to maintain fluency and proficiency in the foreign language.

4. General Recommendation for Building Passive and Active Vocabulary in a Foreign Language

Foreign language learners have two types of vocabulary: passive and active. Passive vocabulary consists of words that a learner can understand when encountered in reading or listening but might not use in speech or writing. In contrast, active vocabulary includes words that a learner can confidently use in speaking and writing. These two types of vocabulary require different approaches for effective development. [2]

The best strategy for acquiring a foreign language efficiently involves learning basic vocabulary and grammar and starting to practice the language actively as soon as possible. Active practice is crucial for keeping knowledge alive and fostering improvement through listening comprehension and reading comprehension.

Progress in foreign language learning should be made in several stages, involving regular review of previously studied words and the accumulation of new ones. For example, if the first phase (A1) consists of learning 200 words, the second phase (A2) would build on this foundation by adding another 200 new words, resulting in a total of 400 words (A1 + 200 new words). The next phase (A3) would further expand the vocabulary to 600 words (A1 + A2 + 200 new words), and so on. This process should continue progressively until reaching a vocabulary of 1500-3000 words. The average repetition rate of all words should be approximately equal to ensure balanced retention and reinforcement.

Recommendations for Building Foreign Language Vocabulary:

- Beginner's Vocabulary (First 200 Words, Total: 200 Words)
- Elementary Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 400 Words)

- Foundational Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 600 Words)
- Basic Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 800 Words)
- Fundamental Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 1000 Words)
- Essential Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 1200 Words)
- Core Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 1400 Words)
- Primary Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 1600 Words)
- Introductory Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 1800 Words)
- Intermediate Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 2000 Words)
- Advanced Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 2200 Words)
- Proficient Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 2400 Words)
- Expert Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 2600 Words)
- Mastery Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 2800 Words)
- Comprehensive Vocabulary (Next 200 Words, Total: 3000 Words)

In addition to structured learning, immersing oneself in the language environment through various media, such as books, articles, movies, and conversations, is essential for expanding both passive and active vocabularies. Listening to native speakers and reading extensively expose learners to new vocabulary in context, aiding in the transition from passive to active use. Learners can build a robust vocabulary and achieve proficiency in the foreign language through regular practice, recommended learning, and repetition.

4.1. Recommendations for Building Foreign Language Passive Vocabulary:

Passive vocabulary consists of foreign language words that are understood while listening or reading but are not actively used in speaking or writing. While crucial for understanding, these words remain unused during active language production.

A learner's passive vocabulary encompasses words understood in context but not necessarily employed in conversation or writing. This knowledge is essential for reading and listening comprehension. For example, a learner might grasp the term "nevertheless" when encountering it in text but refrain from using it orally.

Writing foreign words alongside their translations aids in connecting new vocabulary with familiar concepts, enhancing retention. An illustration: A learner of English may recognize the word "elaborate" in a reading but hesitate to use it in speech or writing.

In essence, passive vocabulary underpins comprehension, paving the way for active vocabulary development. Through consistent exposure and practice, words in the passive vocabulary can transition to active usage. [3], [4]

4.2. Recommendations for Building Foreign Language Active Vocabulary:

Active vocabulary is composed of words understood while listening or reading and confidently used when speaking or writing, facilitating effective communication.

Learners' active vocabulary includes words comfortably integrated into conversation and writing, demonstrating both comprehension and application. For instance, a learner may employ "nevertheless" in both conversation and essay writing.

In writing, active vocabulary involves pairing native language words with their foreign equivalents, reflecting phrases actively used by the learner. For instance, if a learner of English consistently uses "elaborate" in speech and writing, it forms part of their active vocabulary.

Practical language use emphasizes the importance of active vocabulary expansion for effective communication. Regular practice and contextual application enhance fluency and accuracy in a foreign language.

In summary, active vocabulary empowers learners to express themselves confidently and accurately. Consistent practice fosters its growth, enabling fluid communication in a foreign language. [3], [4]

4.3. Some practical steps for building both passive and active language vocabulary.

Building passive and active foreign language vocabulary, along with studying grammar and doing grammar exercises, is part of the daily routine for foreign language acquisition. The recommendation for learners is to start writing their own notebook vocabulary from day one. For passive words, they should begin with foreign words on the left side of the page and their translation into the learner's native language on the right side of the page. For active words, it is the opposite; learners should start with their native language words on the left side of the page and their meaning in the foreign language on the right side of the page.

The right way to acquire passive vocabulary is through listening comprehension and reading comprehension. Engaging with authentic materials such as books, articles, podcasts, and movies in the foreign language helps reinforce this type of vocabulary. The right way to acquire active vocabulary is by explicitly studying the learner's native language's words translated into the foreign language. Practicing speaking and writing in a foreign language, using newly learned active words in various contexts, solidifies their use. In real-life situations, regular revision and use of both passive and active vocabularies will improve overall language fluency and later proficiency.

4.4. Stages of Foreign Language Skills

There are three main stages to learning foreign languages:

- **Beginners:**

- This stage encompasses a vocabulary of about 400–750 passive and active foreign language words and basic grammar skills.

- Learners should pay special attention to their basic vocabulary and use it actively. The active use of basic vocabulary is crucial for progressing to the next stage, where language fluency begins.

– Passive and active vocabularies: Passive vocabulary consists of words that learners can understand when they hear or read them, but do not use frequently in speaking or writing. Active vocabulary consists of words that learners use regularly in their own speech and writing.

– It is extremely important for learners to begin building their active language vocabulary by following the steps outlined in point 3 of the article.

– Basic Grammar Skills: These include foundational grammar rules such as simple sentence structures, verb conjugations, and basic tense usage.

– It is very important for learners to start doing translation exercises from their native language into the foreign language they study.

- **Fluency:**

– This stage encompasses a vocabulary of 750–3000 foreign language words and upper-intermediate grammar skills.

– It is a critical stage because it ensures active use of the language. Learners at this stage should be comfortable using the language in a variety of everyday situations.

– Upper-Intermediate Grammar Skills: These include more complex grammar structures such as conditional sentences, indirect speech, and a wider range of verb tenses and moods.

– Comprehension Vocabulary: This includes understanding and using up to 3000 words, often referenced by tools such as the Oxford 3000, which is a list of the most important and frequently used words in the English language according to the Oxford Dictionaries.

– It is very important for learners to build their active comprehension of foreign language vocabulary, because knowing the basic comprehension vocabulary of Oxford 3000 words is a guarantee for the fluency of the language.

- **Mastery:**

– This stage encompasses a vocabulary of 3000–5000 foreign language words and upper-advanced grammar skills.

– If learners succeed in using the foreign language fluently, they can progress to mastery and proficiency.

– Upper-Advanced Grammar Skills: These include advanced grammatical structures, idiomatic expressions, and subtle nuances in meaning and usage.

– Fluency and Proficiency: Fluency is the ability to speak and understand a language effortlessly and smoothly, whereas proficiency refers to a high level of language competence, including specialized and professional vocabulary.

Additional Explanations:

- Passive and active vocabularies: Passive vocabulary refers to words that learners recognize and understand but do not actively use. Active vocabulary consists of words that learners can use when speaking and writing.

- Grammar Basics: This includes the fundamentals of sentence construction, verb conjugations, and the use of basic tenses.

- Upper-Intermediate Grammar Skills: This involves understanding and using more complex grammatical forms and structures, such as perfect tenses, modals, and clauses.

- The Oxford 3000 and 5000 are lists of the most essential 3000 and 5000 words in English, selected for their importance and frequency of use in both spoken and written communication. [5]

Conclusion:

Foreign language memorization is a multifaceted process that requires recommended approaches to overcome the natural human tendency to forget. The combination of implicit and explicit learning methods, as discussed, plays a crucial role in enhancing memory retention and vocabulary acquisition. Implicit learning through exposure to the language in context, such as listening to native speakers and reading authentic materials, helps build a strong passive vocabulary. Explicit learning, involving structured grammar exercises and deliberate study of vocabulary, facilitates the development of active vocabulary, enabling learners to use new words confidently in speech and writing.

A key recommendation for improving foreign language memorization is to maintain a balanced approach that integrates both implicit and explicit methods. Learners should participate in regular listening and reading activities to reinforce passive vocabulary, as well as speaking and writing exercises to enhance active vocabulary. Vocabulary notebooks serve as an effective tool for organizing and reviewing learned material, listing passive words with their translations and active words with their foreign language equivalents.

The staged approach to vocabulary acquisition, with incremental additions and repeated exposure, ensures long-term retention. Regular practice and review sessions, as well as the use of digital tools such as online dictionaries and language learning apps, further support the memorization process. Immersion in the language environment through multimedia resources and conversations with native speakers aids in the natural transition of words from passive to active memory.

Ultimately, success in foreign language learning lies in the consistent application of these recommendations, tailored to the learner's fluency and later proficiency level. By continuously engaging with the language and employing both implicit and explicit learning techniques, learners can overcome the challenges of memorization, build a robust vocabulary, and achieve proficiency in their foreign language. Regular practice, persistence, and a well-rounded approach will lead to significant improvements in language retention and usage, paving the way for fluency and mastery.

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